

THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN THE ECONOMY

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8170603>

***Abstract.** In this article, the importance of management in today's economy, the possibilities of bringing the art of management to a higher level, the role and importance of strategic management, and scientific and practical proposals and recommendations were developed by the author.*

***Keywords:** management, economy, strategic management, management.*

The main tasks of management are to be able to organize (do) business activities, to be able to see market demand and tradition, linear, official, line-staff leadership structure, territorial structure, elements of production (marketing, business plan, organization, regulation imposing, motivating, controlling, accounting, tending, planning), the art of management and so on.

Professionally trained specialists who have the ability to organize and have a sense of entrepreneurship can be called management. At the same time, he should be able to use many scientific methods in practical activities, he should also be creative.

In the organization of management process (organization, technology, planning), business plan and supply, financing and business plan, price formation and borrowing, etc. must provide.

Modern enterprises (enterprises, organizations) must choose products and purchase resources in order to operate in market conditions. In a market economy, all problems are solved by the market itself.

Every element in the planning and execution of the manager's work results from some unexpected requirements.

When a manager attempts to predict the volume of output to be produced or grown, he must remember that price is a key element in the demand mechanism. In order to increase the volume of products in the market, it is necessary to reduce the price of the product. It is difficult to control the market process. It is necessary to know the market mechanism that interacts with supply and demand, price formation, and other such traditions. Here is not only a product (service), but also production skills of employees involved in production (production, service) are also important.

Strategic management in an enterprise can be in the form of a linear, executive, line-staff, "by product" organizational structure.

All tasks of management in a linear organizational structure are in the hands (position, discretion) of the department manager. In the executive structure, the manager specializes in a specific field of activity and is responsible for it. In a linear-staff organizational structure, planning, accounting and control issues are solved more competently.

Management in the organizational structure "by product" is more complicated, it is an advanced form of the traditional linear-functional structure in the conditions of the automatic system of enterprise management.

The content of management reveals its task. The strategic task of management: the structure of the network economy; its territorial structure; separate elements of production (service). Their

specific tasks: marketing, business plan, organization, regulation (adjustment), promotion, control, accounting, inclination, planning, forecasting.

The necessary structure and content of the strategic tasks of management should be given attention (unbiased), otherwise the effectiveness will decrease.

Management work is related to social, spiritual, economic, pedagogical, professional and other disciplines. Using their recommendations increases the art of management. Thus, in order to understand the nature of strategic tasks of management, it is necessary to jointly imagine its relationship with the concepts of categories. On the one hand, economy, market, entrepreneurship, marketing are assumed, and on the other hand, each of these concepts enters the management system as an element in the expression of self-selection, and takes the form of a unified form. As a result, an organizational structure of management appears.

An enterprise or organization may have plans developed, appropriate structure, effective information transmission, installation of modern equipment and innovative technologies. But if the members of the enterprise (organization, enterprise) do not work (do not show activity) as required, all opportunities will be destroyed. An employee is not a machine, he should be able to "connect" if he needs to work. In order for an employee to be effectively managed, he must have a qualified readiness, desire, sincerity, good looks, motivation, mood, frustration, that is, inclination.

Inclination is a set of internal and external driving forces that encourage a person to act, gives a limit and shape to the activity, shows a direction to the activity, and sets the way to achieve certain goals.

In order to understand the description of inclination, it is necessary to be able to define the characteristics of activities such as human need, reason, motivational factors, effort, determination, honesty, and focus on a goal.

An employee can do a job with different efforts. So it can act differently. Inclination is a set of forces aimed at forcing a person to work, at a certain level of action, to achieve goals with a certain degree of determination and honesty.

The inclination process and consists of the following steps:

- emergence of needs;
- search for ways to eliminate needs;
- determining the course of action;
- performing an action;
- make an effort to encourage;
- elimination of needs.

These are variable. Therefore, there are theories about the content and process of addiction. The theory of dispositional content is aimed at forcing the human mind to act. The theory of the dispositional process states that a person acts on a certain behavior. It is the process of motivating someone to achieve a goal. Needs can be met with incentives. It is necessary to study the mechanism, content, price, and solution of promotion. Theories related to the dispositional process include expectancy theory, goal setting theory, and participative management theory (participation in organizational activities).

A group in a strategic management system is two or more people, each of whom has a different influence at the same time and feels its influence. Management voluntarily creates

groups, that is, organizational structure units in the enterprise (accountants, planning and other departments). These are official groups.

As soon as the formal enterprise (organization, enterprise, corporation) and groups are created, it again becomes a social environment in which employees interact in ways that the leader does not want. From social interactions, many friendly groups, informal groups begin to appear, all of which take the form of an informal enterprise (organization, enterprise). An informal enterprise is a self-created group of people who regularly interact to achieve certain goals.

If any changes are made in the official enterprise, the informal enterprise will protest. For example, the introduction of new technology affects groups, their roles and situations change. Changes in which the people who perceive it become unbiased (objective) threaten groups. Management encourages participants in the adopted solution to reduce resistance. Informal enterprises, like formal enterprises, have their own leaders. The informal leader achieves his position, that is, he has and applies a position on his attitude to the group members. This is where an informal leader has the same opportunity to influence employees as a formal company leader.

An informal leader helps to achieve the group's goal, enforces and reinforces its functioning. Informal enterprises interact with formal enterprises from time to time, and it is important for managers to understand this.

Managing informal enterprise requires acknowledging and understanding the existence of informal enterprise, working with them instead of intimidating them. It is necessary to listen to the opinions of members and leaders of informal groups, it is useful to make the right conclusions.

Employees and labor teams in the enterprise are formed by mutual relations. Economic systems, organizational structures, their work methods, economic criteria in the management of an enterprise (organization, enterprise, corporation) are formed by the interaction of individuals with each other. The economic and social activities of employees in the enterprise are interrelated. The content of the interdependence problem: what is the behavior; adding an employee to the scope of the enterprise. The work of an employee in an enterprise is a process of continuous interaction with the scope of the enterprise. The employee expects a lot of needs from the company, and the company also expects a lot from the employee.

Every employee can "go through" the process of entering an enterprise (enterprise, organization, corporation) several times in his life. Being in an enterprise, being a member of it, and entering an enterprise and remaining a member of it are not the same thing.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the successful operation of the enterprise, the priority sign of the enterprise's potential, its strategic views, the stages of development as a part of the economy ensure its perfect action in the following cases. These include:

- the use of preferred means to achieve the company's goals;
- principles, rules and norms of the enterprise as a whole organism;
- includes the standards of conduct necessary for the employee to perform his duties.

REFERENCES

1. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand-2023
2. Musaeva Sh.A. Integrated marketing communication Study guide "Maharat" publishing house, Samarkand - 2022

3. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
4. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
5. Usmonova Dिल्фуза Ilkhomovna, EXAMINATION OF THE INVESTMENT PROJECT OF LEASING COMPANY SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337